

Impact Damage Resistance of Laminated Composites With Toughened Interfaces

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was performed to study the effect of interface toughening on impact damage of laminated composites resulting from low-velocity impact. The extent of delaminations in the materials resulting from the impact was utilized to characterize the impact resistance.

Low-velocity impact tests were performed on the T300/976 graphite/epoxy composite with and without FM300 thermoset interleaves, the T800H/3900-2 graphite/epoxy composite with thermoplastic interface coatings, and the graphite/PEEK thermoplastic matrix composites. All the specimens were tested by an impactor with a spherical steel head.

Numerical calculations were also performed using the 3DIMPACT code to correlate with the impact damage found in the laminates. Based on the study, it demonstrated that appropriate interface toughening can be an effective means to improve impact resistance of laminated composites.

Keywords: Impact Resistance, Delamination, Laminated Composites, Interleaves

1. INTRODUCTION

Impact damage has been a major concern in the design of organic matrix laminated composite structures, because these materials are vulnerable to transverse impact. Impact can produce significant internal damage in the materials, especially delamination failure.

Both thermoset and thermoplastic interleaves have been demonstrated in the literature to be effective in suppressing free-edge delamination growth in laminates. Carlsson et al [1,2] showed that the toughening interleaves can improve considerably interfacial fracture toughnesses in laminates. It has also been shown [3,4] that toughening interleaves can improve impact resistance of laminated composites. Therefore, it is important to understand fundamentally the mechanics and mechanisms of interface-toughened composites relating to impact and the relationship between the interleaf properties and impact damage growth in the composites.

This paper will summarize the preliminary result from an on-going study on characterizing and modeling the effect of interface toughening on impact resistance

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of laminated composites. Both experiments and analyses were conducted. All the specimens were X-rayed before the tests. Each specimen was only tested once and then immediately X-rayed. The overall delamination size was measured. Some specimens were also sliced and examined microscopically to determine the internal damage.

Impact damage was also predicted by using the 3DIMPACT code which was developed previously by Choi and Chang [5] for predicting impact damage in organic matrix laminated composites subjected to low-velocity point impact. The code can provide information on the impact velocity corresponding to the initial impact damage and estimate the extent of delamination in each interface of the laminates.

II. RESULTS AND COMPARISON

Figure 1 shows the comparison of the impact damage size in T300/976 composites between the laminates with and without FM300 thermoset interleaves. The FM300 interleaf has been shown to improve the interfacial Mode I fracture toughness more effectively than the interfacial Mode II fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy composites [1, 2]. Liu and Chang [6] showed that interlaminar (or interfacial) Mode I fracture toughness strongly affected the initiation of delamination induced by matrix cracking in laminated composites resulting from impact, while the interfacial Mode II and III fracture toughnesses are more important than Mode I fracture toughness for delamination growth due to impact.

Apparently, the laminates with interleaves delayed the initiation of the impact damage and produced a smaller damage size as compared to the laminates without the interleaves. For instance, at an impact velocity of 5.4 m/s, the projected delamination area in the interleaved composites was less than 50% of the damage area found in the laminates without interleaves. The predictions based on the "3DIMPACT" code correlated well with the data for the laminates without interleaves. No comparison was made for the interleaved composites because of the lack of material property data for the interleaved composites at the time of preparation of the manuscript.

For the T800H/3900-2 composite which was coated with a thin polyimide thermoplastic film during manufacturing [7], the impact damage size was found to be smallest among all the materials compared. It was reported [7] that the polyimide interface films improved significantly the Mode II interface fracture toughness of the T800H/3900-2 composite. For instance, the Mode II fracture toughness of the T800H/3900-2 composite is about ten times bigger than that of the T300/976 composite.

Figure 2 shows the comparison between the data and the predictions based on the "3DIMPACT" code. Again, the predictions agreed well with the data. As a comparison, the predicted impact damage areas for the T300/976 thermoset composite, the graphite/PEEK thermoplastic composite, and the T800H/3900-2 interface-toughened composite were presented in Figure 3. Apparently, the T800H/3900-2 thermoset composite toughened with the thermoplastic films demonstrated the highest impact resistance. The thermoplastic PEEK composite performed better than the T300/976 thermoset composite without interleaves.

III. CONCLUSIONS

It was demonstrated that interface toughening can improve significantly the impact resistance of laminated composites to low-velocity impact. Delamination growth induced by impact can be adequately suppressed by appropriately toughening the laminate interfaces. It seems to indicate that the interlaminar Mode I fracture toughness affects considerably the delamination initiation resulting from impact, but the interlaminar Mode II and III fracture toughnesses become increasingly important as the delamination grows away from the impacted area.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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Figure 1. The projected delamination area from X-radiographs of impacted specimens. Comparison of impact damage in T300/976 composites between the laminates with and without FM300 interleaves.

Figure 2. Comparison between the data and the predictions of the projected delamination area in T800/3900-2 composites resulting from impact.

Figure 3. The projected delamination area as a function of impact velocity for three different composite material systems.